

3-Bromo-2-(2'-methoxyphenyl)chromones (5a-g): Cupric bromide (3 mol) was dissolved in refluxing chloroform-ethyl acetate mixture (1:2). The chromone (4a-g) (1 mol) was then added to it and the reflux continued for 8–12 h. The grey white precipitate of copper(I) bromide was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness and the solid residue was crystallised from suitable solvents. All the compounds (Table 1) gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

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References

1. K. D. BANERJI and D. PODDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1119; D. P. SARBAGGYA, K. RANGACHARI, A. K. D. MAZUMDAR and K. D. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 196; A. K. D. MAZUMDAR, G. C. SAHA, T. K. SINHA and K. D. BANERJI, *J. Nep. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **4**, 1.
2. K. D. BANERJI and D. PODDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 584; P. M. WADODKAR and M. G. MARATHEV, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 145.
3. A. K. D. MAZUMDAR, G. C. SAHA, T. K. SINHA and K. D. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 996.

Synthesis of some Tetrahydropyrimidines

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HYDROPYRIMIDINES¹ and hydrazine derivatives² are reported to possess diverse biological and pharmacological properties. Keeping this in view, we have undertaken the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some 4-aryl-5-(arylhiazinocarbamoyl)-6-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-ones (Scheme 1).

Aromatic aldehydes undergo Biginatti's reaction to give pyrimidine derivatives³, which react with various hydrazine derivatives to form the titled compounds (2). Aldehydes used were 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromo- and 5-iodovaniline.

In the ir spectra of compounds 2, the disappearance of the peak at 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O ester) and the appearance of a peak at 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide) proved the conversion of 1 to 2.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir

- 1a**; Ar=2-OH-5-Br.C₆H₃
1b; Ar=4-OH-5-I-3-OCH₃.C₆H₂
1c; Ar=4-OH-5-Br-3-OCH₃.C₆H₂

Compounds 2:

- 2a-e**; Ar=2-OH-5-Br.C₆H₃
2f-j; Ar=4-OH-5-I-3-OCH₃.C₆H₂
2k-o; Ar=4-OH-5-Br-3-OCH₃.C₆H₂
2a, f, k; Ar'=H **2d, i, n**; Ar'=COC₆H₅
2b, g, l; Ar'=C₆H₅ **2e, j, o**; Ar'=COC₆H₅-NH₂-4
2c, h, m; Ar'=2,4-(NO₂)₂.C₆H₃.

Scheme 1

spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-Oxo-6-methyl-5-carbethoxy-4-aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidines (1). General procedure: A mixture of the aldehyde (0.5 mol), urea (0.5 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.75 mol) in absolute ethanol (200 ml) and concentrated HCl (a few drops) was refluxed for 3 h. It was then chilled and the product was filtered. The filtrate was refluxed for 1.5 h and the solvent partially distilled off and then cooled to yield solid product. The solid was then recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

4-Aryl-5-(arylhiazinocarbamoyl)-6-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-2-ones (2): A mixture of compound 1 (0.01 mol) and various hydrazine derivatives (0.01 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (30 ml) for 3 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1): ν_{max} (KBr) 3300 (NH), 1690 (C=O cyclic), 1640 (C=O non-cyclic), 1320 (C-N bend) and 1490 cm⁻¹ (C=C bend).

Results and Discussion

In the antibacterial screening, out of 15 compounds tested, 8 compounds (**2a, e, f, i, k, l, n, o**)

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₄	224	86
1b	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ IN ₂ O ₆	210	85
1c	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₆	206	85
2a	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₅	94	81
2b	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₅	196	79
2c	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₇	152	73
2d	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₄	136	79
2e	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ BrN ₄ O ₄	113	72
2f	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ IN ₄ O ₄	142	83
2g	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ IN ₄ O ₄	159	82
2h	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ IN ₄ O ₈	119	70
2i	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ IN ₄ O ₆	126	77
2j	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ IN ₄ O ₆	122	76
2k	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₄	133	80
2l	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₄	192	74
2m	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O ₈	131	73
2n	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₆	126	81
2o	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ BrN ₄ O ₆	180	74

*All the compounds showed satisfactory results for N analyses.

were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 5 compounds (2b, c, e, f, k) active against *E. coli*; thus 3 compounds (2e, f, k) were found active against both the species.

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References

1. A. KARPANOV, A. GALABOV, D. SIDZHAKOVA and D. DANCHEV, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 27366; T. WAKABAYASHI, M. SHIMIZU, K. INOUE and H. KATAYAMA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 167498; J. KREPELEKA, M. MELKA, R. KOTVA, M. SIMONOVA, J. VACHERK and J. HOLUBEK, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 32977; M. TERANISHI, T. MURAGATA, M. MATSUKUMA, K. SHUTO and S. ICHIKAWA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 107921; V. KATSONS, R. VITOLINS, E. I. KHANINA, G. DUBURS and A. A. KIMENIS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 16014; S. EVANGELISTA, R. PIRISINO, F. PERRETTI, R. FANTOZZI, S. BRUNHILESCHI, P. MOLMBERYAIELLO and A. BARTOLIN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 49166.
2. J. SUPNIESKI, T. BENY and J. KRUPINSKA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, **50**, 7800; D. LIBERMANN, N. RIST, F. GRUMBACH, M. MOYBUX, B. GAUTHIER, A. ROUAIX, J. MAILLARD, J. HIMBERT and S. CALS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, **50**, 351; O. CHEN, F. LIU and L. XIE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 186698; D. L. RECTOR, G. A. CONDAR and S. D. FOLZ, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, **108**, 167292.
3. K. FOLKERS, H. J. HARWOOD and T. B. JOHNSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3754.

Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of 2-Hydroxy-4,6-diphenylpyrimidines

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PYRIMIDINES have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities¹. With a view to getting better therapeutic activity, some new pyrimidines of type 4 were synthesised.

2-Hydroxyacetophenones (1) were condensed with benzoyl chloride or *p*-anisoyl chloride to get the respective *o*-aroyloxyacetophenones (2) which were then treated with KOH-pyridine to get 2'-hydroxydibenzoylmethanes² (3). Compounds 3 were condensed with urea in ethylene glycol (solvent) to obtain 2-hydroxy-4-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidines³ (4) (Scheme 1). The structural assign-

Scheme 1